

EFFECTIVENESS OF THAT.QUIZ ON EXAM PERFORMANCE AND STUDENT ENGAGEMENT: BASIS FOR IMPLEMENTING INTERACTIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

The research titled "Effectiveness of That.quiz on Exam Performance and Student Engagement: Basis for Implementing Interactive Learning Strategies" conducted at Full Bright College, Palawan, Philippines, aims to assess the impact of That.quiz on the engagement and academic performance of second-year Criminology students. Employing a quantitative research design, a survey was conducted among 30 participants using random sampling techniques to explore their preferences and experiences with That.quiz in comparison to traditional face-to-face methods. The findings of the study reveal a high level of student engagement (weighted mean = 3.85) and above-average academic performance (weighted mean = 4.21) when That.quiz is employed. However, a comparative analysis with face-to-face methods indicates a higher mean score of 31.03 for the traditional approach, implying its sustained efficacy. Noteworthy is the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating a substantial difference in exam performance and affirming the positive impact of incorporating That.quiz into the learning process. This conclusion, drawn at a 5% level of significance, underscores the transformative potential of technology-enhanced quizzes on student academic achievements. The research design encompassed survey administration, and data analysis employed descriptive statistics, offering a comprehensive overview of the study's purpose, methodology, analysis process, and key results. The study's contribution lies in providing valuable insights into the dynamic relationship between technology-enhanced learning tools, specifically That.quiz, and student outcomes within the field of Criminology. These

insights serve as a foundation for the potential implementation of interactive learning strategies in academic settings.

Keywords: *Online, That.quiz, Interactive Learning, Student Engagement, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of education, the integration of technology has become pivotal in shaping interactive learning experiences. A study was made by Lazlo (1995) wherein it focuses on the effectiveness of various interactive technologies, and they suggested during that time that future generations of learners are more likely to be interested in the learning process when interactive learning tools were utilized. As traditional teaching methods evolve, it is imperative to offer new avenues of learning to enhance the engagement of students and their academic performance. The E-learning theory implies that educational technology can have a great impact on the enhancement of the effectiveness of learning through the usage of multimedia. This theory belongs to the grand unified theory of Connectivism; a theory that accepts the crucial role technology plays in the learning process. This research focuses on the effectiveness of That.quiz, a digital platform designed to enhance both outcomes and student engagement.

The effectiveness of That.quiz on exam performance and student engagement stands out as a cornerstone for interactive learning, especially during the pandemic but later was adapted to be used in assessing the examination performance of Criminology students at Fullbright College. A study was conducted by Lydia (2022) about the impact of online tools on the learning experience of students and it was found that the usage of online tools such as “Socrative apps” may improve student engagement, motivation, and participation in class as well as their ability to retain important learning materials. By seamlessly integrating technology into the learning process, That.quiz not only gauges students’ understanding but also fosters active participation. Wang (2021) states in their study that with the data analysis feature of clever interactive tools, teachers can also ascertain each student's current learning status and provide tailored guidance to boost learning motivation. Through personalized assessments, That.quiz tailors content delivery to individual students' needs, cultivating a targeted approach to learning. Moreover, That.quiz provides a real-time feedback mechanism that empowers teachers to identify and address their students’ weaknesses promptly, enhancing exam preparation. Elements within That. quiz elevates students' engagement, transforming the learning experience into an interactive and enjoyable journey of learning.

Research Questions

The main problem addressed by this study is to identify the effectiveness of the utilization of That.quiz in the exam performance and students' engagement in the learning process of the 2nd year BS Criminology Students of Fullbright College A.Y. 2023-2024. Specifically, it shall attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
2. What are the factors that affect the utilization of that quiz for students?
3. How effective is the utilization of That.quiz in the engagement in terms of;
 - 3.1. Students' Engagement
 - 3.2. Exam Performance
4. Is there a significant difference between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and the current exam performance of the student when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process?

Based on the theoretical framework and existing literature, the following hypotheses are proposed for this study:

Null Hypothesis (Ho)- There is a significant difference between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and the current exam performance of the student when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process.

Alternative Hypothesis (Ha)- There is no significant difference between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and the current exam performance of the student when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design to systematically investigate the impact of That.quiz on exam performance and student engagement in Criminology education. The quantitative approach was chosen for its ability to provide measurable outcomes and facilitate statistical analysis. The study aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the influence of interactive learning strategies on academic outcomes, combining quantitative data with insights into students' perceptions.

The research focuses on assessing students' perceptions of That.quiz in the learning process. Informed consent will be obtained from 2nd-year BS Criminology students at Fullbright College, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan. A survey questionnaire will

explore factors influencing That.quiz adoption, including students' engagement and exam performance. Exam results will be collected with participant consent to evaluate the tool's effectiveness. The study follows ethical standards with approved consent procedures, confidentiality, and data security measures in place.

Data collection involves the distribution of an online questionnaire via a Google form to a randomly selected sample of 2nd-year BS Criminology students. Microsoft Excel is used for data analysis, with the Data Analysis Tool Pack confirming the reliability and validity of the study. The examination of hypotheses utilizes the Two Paired T-Test, chosen for its appropriateness in comparing means within a paired sample design.

RESULTS

In this study, the Data Analysis Tool Pack was employed to validate and ensure the questionnaire items met rigorous reliability standards. Additionally, the statistical analyses utilized the Two Paired T-Test and weighted mean to assess variations across different survey questions. This approach not only ensured robustness in the evaluation process but also provided a comprehensive understanding of the nuanced aspects captured by the questionnaire.

1. Profile of the respondents

Figure 1: Age of the Respondents

Figure 2: Gender of the Respondents

2. What are the factors that affect the utilization of That.quiz for students?

Figure 3: Factors that affect the utilization of That.quiz for students

3. How effective is the utilization of That.quiz in the engagement in terms of;
- 3.1. Students' Engagement
 - 3.2. Exam Performance

Table 1. Student Engagement

Statements	5	4	3	2	1	TWF	WM	Verbal Description
1. How frequently do you engage with that.quiz as part of your coursework?	11	13	2	4	0	121	4.03	Frequently
2. Do that.quiz enhance your engagement with course content?	10	4	10	6	0	108	3.6	Very Much
3. Have that.quiz increased your motivation to study?	13	5	3	7	2	110	3.67	Very Much
4. Do you feel more involved in the course due to the use of that.quiz?	10	14	5	1	0	123	4.1	Very Much
Overall Weighted Mean							3.85	Very Much

Legend:

4.51-5.00 – Very Frequently / Extremely
 3.51-4.50 – Frequently / Very Much
 2.51-3.50 – Occasionally / Moderately
 1.51-2.50 – Rarely / Slightly
 1.00-1.50 – Never / Not at all

Table 2. Academic Performance

Statements	5	4	3	2	1	TWF	WM	Verbal Description
1. Do you find that.quiz helpful for reinforcing course material?	11	14	4	0	1	124	4.13	Agree
2. How would you rate your academic performance in courses that utilize that.quiz?	16	5	8	1	0	126	4.2	Above Average
3. Do you believe your grades have improved since the incorporation of that.quiz?	18	8	0	3	1	129	4.3	Moderately
Overall Weighted Mean							4.21	Above Average

Legend:

4.51-5.00 – Strongly Agree / Excellent / Significantly
 3.51-4.50 – Agree / Above Average / Moderately
 2.51-3.50 – Neutral / Average / Undecided
 1.51-2.50 – Disagree / Below Average / Not really
 1.00-1.50 – Strongly Disagree / Poor/ Not at all

4. Is there a significant difference between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and the current exam performance of the student when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process?

Table 3. Utilization vs. Non-utilization of That.quiz during quizzes

Variables	Mn	SD	t value	t critical	Decision
Quiz Scores of BS-2 Crim. Students in That.quiz	27.29	5.82	±5.65	±2.04	Reject Null Hypothesis
Quiz Scores of BS-2 Crim. Students in Face to face	31.03	5.46			

DISCUSSION

The study reveals that, out of a total of 30 respondents, the results indicate that 53% (16 respondents) were aged 20-21, while only 7% (2 respondents) were aged 18-19. This implies that the majority of the respondents (53%) were between 20 and 21 years old, indicating they are old enough to understand the study.

It also shows that the majority of respondents, identified as Criminology students, were male, constituting 97% (29 respondents), while only 3% (1 respondent) were female. This suggests a strong preference among males for the Criminology course.

The primary factor influencing students' use of That.quiz is internet connection, making up 60%, while the allotted time for use has the lowest percentage at 15%. Sun et al. (2008) supported this finding, stating that if online courses have poor technology, frequent technical issues, and slow response times, students may be discouraged from participating.

The majority of respondents indicated frequent involvement with That.quiz as an integral component of their coursework, assigning it a weighted mean of 4.03. Furthermore, participants expressed that That.quiz significantly enhanced their engagement, boosted their motivation to study, and made them feel more immersed in the course, with weighted means of 3.6, 3.67, and 4.1, respectively.

Hence, there is a high level of student engagement with That.quiz, reflected in an overall weighted mean of 3.85.

A significant majority of respondents concurred that they perceive That.quiz as beneficial for reinforcing course material, attributing it a weighted mean of 4.13. Furthermore, a substantial majority of participants also rated their academic performance as above average in courses incorporating That.quiz, assigning it a weighted mean of 4.2. Additionally, almost all respondents expressed a moderate belief that their grades have improved since the integration of That.quiz.

Thus, the academic performance of students using That.quiz is above average, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 4.21.

Additionally, it is evident that the Quiz Scores of BS-2 Criminology students during face-to-face sessions were better, with a mean of 31.03 compared to their Quiz Scores in That.quiz, which had a weighted mean of 27.29.

It can also be gleaned that the two variables were almost consistent, with a standard deviation of 5.82 and 5.46, with That.quiz having a higher standard deviation.

Moreover, the researchers reject the null hypothesis (H_0) since the computed t-value of ± 5.65 was higher than the critical t-value of 2.0 and lower than -2.04. Rejecting

the null hypothesis means that there is a significant difference between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and their current exam performance when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process, using a 5% level of significance.

Conclusions

Based on the research questions and data analysis, it has provided valuable insights into the profile of respondents, factors influencing the utilization of the quiz, and the effectiveness of That.quiz utilization on students' engagement and exam performance. First, we explored the demographic profile of the respondents, examining both age and gender. The analysis revealed that the majority of respondents in terms of age fell within the 20 to 21 range, indicating a concentrated age group within the study participants. Gender-wise, the study revealed that the majority of respondents were male, highlighting a notable gender distribution among those involved.

An essential aspect explored was the identification of factors affecting the utilization of the That.quiz for students. The majority of respondents pointed to internet connection as a key factor influencing quiz utilization. This emphasizes the importance of addressing technological infrastructure as a critical consideration in the successful integration of interactive tools like quizzes into the learning process.

Regarding the effectiveness of quiz utilization, the study found that That.quiz significantly enhanced students' engagement, providing a notable boost in motivation. The findings suggest that incorporating quizzes into the learning process can be a powerful strategy to enhance student participation, making the educational experience more interactive and engaging educational experience. Moreover, the impact of That.quiz utilization on exam performance was investigated. While the results may vary, the study suggests a positive correlation between the incorporation of "That.quiz" and improvements in exam performance. This underscores the potential of interactive tools to positively influence academic outcomes, providing educators and institutions with valuable insights into effective pedagogical approaches. In addressing the question of a significant difference in exam performance between periods with and without That.quiz utilization, the study found evidence that between the previous exam performance of the students when That.quiz is not utilized during the learning process and their current exam performance when That.quiz is utilized during the learning process supporting the positive impact of using "That.quiz" during the learning process. The data revealed a statistically significant difference, indicating that the integration of That.quiz contributed to an improvement in overall exam performance.

In summary, the findings of this study not only shed light on the demographic profile and influencing factors but also underscore the positive effects of That.quiz integration on student engagement and exam performance. These insights are crucial for educators and institutions aiming to enhance the educational experience and outcomes for students, particularly in the context of digital learning environments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers propose the following recommendations:

1. **Integration of That.quiz in Criminology Courses:** Fullbright College should consider integrating That.quiz as a regular component in Criminology courses, leveraging its positive impact on student engagement and academic performance.
2. **Professional Development for Faculty:** Faculty members should undergo training and professional development sessions to familiarize themselves with the effective utilization of That.quiz and other technology-enhanced learning tools. This will enable them to maximize the benefits of these tools in their teaching methods.
3. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regular monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of That.quiz should be conducted to assess its ongoing impact on student outcomes. This includes collecting feedback from students and faculty to make necessary adjustments and improvements.
4. **Exploration of Other Interactive Learning Tools:** While That.quiz has shown positive results, exploring and incorporating other interactive learning tools can further diversify the learning experience. This can include virtual simulations, discussion forums, and collaborative projects that align with the Criminology curriculum.
5. **Further Research:** Future research can delve deeper into the specific aspects of That.quiz that contribute to student engagement and academic performance. Additionally, comparative studies with other interactive learning tools can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the most effective strategies in Criminology education.

Implementing these recommendations will contribute to the continuous improvement of teaching methodologies and the overall learning experience for Criminology students at Fullbright College.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study affirm that all necessary measures were taken to ensure the ethical integrity of the research. Informed consent was diligently obtained from all participants, explicitly outlining the purpose, procedures, and potential implications of the study. Respondents were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the research at any stage without consequence, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their participation.

Strict measures were implemented to maintain the anonymity of the respondents throughout the research process. Identifiable information was handled with utmost

confidentiality to protect the privacy of the participants. No personal details were disclosed in any publications or presentations arising from this study.

Furthermore, the well-being of the respondents was prioritized, and they were not exposed to any form of harm, whether physical, emotional, or psychological, during the course of the research. The research design and execution adhered to ethical guidelines to mitigate potential risks and ensure a secure environment for the participants.

To uphold the integrity of the study, the authors affirm that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of the research. The research was driven solely by academic and scientific objectives, and there was no external influence that could compromise the impartiality and objectivity of the findings.

Plagiarism was rigorously avoided in all aspects of the research process. The authors adhered to ethical writing practices, giving due credit to existing literature and properly citing sources. Originality and academic honesty were paramount in presenting a credible and trustworthy study.

Moreover, there was a commitment to impartiality in the interpretation of the findings. The data was analyzed objectively, and results were reported without bias or manipulation. The authors recognize the importance of presenting a transparent and unbiased account of the research outcomes.

Lastly, the results of this study were used purely for research purposes. The findings contribute to the academic discourse and aim to enhance the understanding utilization of That.quiz to enhance students' performance. The utilization of the results remains within the boundaries of ethical research practices, ensuring that the knowledge generated is disseminated responsibly and ethically.

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